

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF FINTECH IN FINANCIAL SERVICES OF BANKING SECTOR

Dr. Veda D. Malagatti

Associate Professor, IBMR, Hubballi, Karnataka State

Afsana Gudagi

MBA 2nd year, IBMR, Hubballi, Karnataka State

Kanchan Singh

MBA 2nd year, IBMR, Hubballi, Karnataka State

ABSTRACT

Fundamentally, financial services digitalization makes use of Fintech to boost productivity, increase accessibility, and encourage innovation. The Fintech sector in India is witnessing emerging trend and accounts to 14% share of Global Funding. Fintech refers to the integration of technology into offerings by financial services companies to improve their use and delivery to consumers. The Fintech Market Opportunity is estimated to be \$2.1 Tn by 2030. Objective of the study is to summarise the perception and satisfaction of the users of various digital based services used for processing the transactions, payments, transfers etc by using either online banking service or digital wallets or mobile apps offered by the banks. Assessment about the constraints faced and analyze whether such challenges can be easily tackled to bring in the transformation towards blooming digital era. Primary data is collected using tool of questionnaire and convenience sampling techniques is used where respondents are of all age group and some have occupation. T Test, correlation and regression is used to prove about the affirmation of growing trend and the expected futuristic trend of Fintech which is a blooming one in future.

Keywords: Fintech, Services, Digital, Users, Banking

Cite this Article: Dr. Veda D. Malagatti, Afsana Gudagi, Kanchan Singh, A Study on Impact of Fintech in Financial Services of Banking Sector, International Journal of Management (IJM), 15(4), 2024, pp. 177-199.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJM/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_4/IJM_15_04_015.pdf

INTRODUCTION

Technological breakthroughs have brought about a dramatic change in the financial services business, known as digitalization, which is changing the face of the sector. The implementation of Fintech in financial operations, ranging from consumer interactions to backend procedures, is part of this transition that is reshaping the way financial services are provided and used.. The automation of repetitive operations and procedures lowers operating costs and speeds up service delivery, making it one of the main advantages.

Digital Payments by UPI crossed the landmark 10 Bn transactions from just 1 Mn transactions in 2016. Digital Payments increased by 76% in transactions and 91% in value (2022). A pan-India digital payments survey (covering 90,000 respondents) revealed that 42% of respondents have used digital payments and this had facilitated with the increase in infrastructure for digital payments of 34%. India already has the 2nd highest number of smartphone users globally and is the 2nd largest Internet user market.. The number of households with internet connections are expected with an increase by 46%, reaching 233 Mn households by 2026, compared to 160 Mn in 2021. 68% of India's population is young and is estimated to add middle-income and high-income households which will drive the demand and growth of Indian FinTech space. Indian Fintech startups raised \$5.65 Bn and institutional investors almost doubled from 535 to 1019 in 2022. Fintech have expanded financial inclusion and use technology to cut down on operational costs.

Furthermore, increased access using digitization fosters expansion of financial inclusion. to underserved and unbanked communities. People who live in rural places may obtain financial services without going to physical branches thanks to digital wallets and mobile banking. Fintech solutions enable low-income people to engage in the formal economy by providing microloans and insurance products that are suited to their requirements. This inclusiveness promotes economic growth by bridging the gap between various socio-economic groups. Furthermore, Fintech provide individualized client experiences through data analytics and artificial intelligence (AI). This shift toward individualized banking experiences reflects a larger trend toward customer-centricity in financial services by providing apps which are user friendly, where digital capabilities has fuelled innovation in financial services. Technology is being used by both traditional institutions and fintech startups to provide innovative solutions like robo-advisors, peer-to-peer lending platforms, and blockchain-based payment systems. These innovations are changing the industry's old business structures by improving accessibility, financial efficiency, and transparency in addition to meeting changing customer demands.

However along with these advantages, financial services digitization brings with it several vulnerable challenges that need to be successfully overcome. Furthermore, the financial industry sees changes in deployment of labor workforce who integrate management with high speed of technological development brought about by digitalization. Traditional jobs may be replaced by automation and AI-driven processes; therefore, employees need to sharpen their skills and competences to stay competitive in using the Fintech and expected emerging digital era.

LITERATURE REVIEW

(2023), Amit Shrivastava, Ajay Mishra, Pooja Talreja conducted research on **‘An Analysis of the Role of ICT in Digitalization of Banking Financial Services & Insurance Sector’**. The research states that the banking sector's biggest challenge today is modernization with technology network that will unify urban and rural areas under sustainable development, ensuring social inclusivity. . As banks undergo a technological transformation, they encounter disruptive technologies requiring extensive adaptation of collaboration strategies. On (2023), Kuppani Sathish, Jayendra Gopal Thatipudi, P. Manikandan, N. Kanthimathi, T. Srinivasa Rao, P Alexander, conducted research on **‘Blockchain based Enhancement of Digital Revolution in Financial Sector’**. The research states that Digitalization alters enterprise interactions and the sector's structure, resulting in new business models, transformed value chains, new product delivery channels, and more. However, academics have yet to adapt these strategic shifts of Fintech for sustainability or the future directions of the financial industry. Financial technology notably revamps traditional models to better serve loyal customers by enhancing digital access channels, solutions, and product options. On March (2024), Rahul Singh Gautam, Mobashshir Siddiqui, Nishant Panda, Shailesh Rastogi, Ravi Teja Gannamaraju, conducted research on **‘Digitalization of Financial Services and its Impact on Sustainable Development Goals in India’**. The results indicate a significant positive effect of digitalized financial services on SDGs. However, the study highlights challenges in financial literacy and infrastructure that the government needs to address to optimize digital service delivery. On (2023), Deepa Pillai, Ardhendu Shekhar Singh, Trupti Bhosale, Adesh Doifode, conducted research on **‘A Perspective on the Application of Fintech as a Gateway for Financial Literacy’**. The research states that AI-powered fintech can tackle complex financial problems and provide adaptable support. Despite current efforts of growing use of fintech in emerging nations, coupled with increased smartphone ownership, revolutionized digital literacy and financial inclusion, a gap remains that still fintech tools can bridge. On October 31, 2022, P. G. Thirumagal, T. Das, S. Das, E. Khatri, K. S. and S. Rani, conducted research on **‘The Role of IoT in Revolutionizing Payment Systems and Digital Transactions in Finance’**.

The research paper explores how Internet of Things (IoT) innovations are speeding up payment processes, lowering transaction costs, and reducing fraud. Additionally, it examines how IoT promotes financial inclusion by offering digital payment services to previously underserved groups to leverage the transformation of Fintech. In (2023), Namrata Kapoor Kohli, Timsy Kapoor, Vidya Telang, conducted research on **‘Digital Payment System as a Growth Driver for the Indian Economy an Analysis’**. The objective of this study examines that Digitalization is a key growth driver in today's economy, offering advantages like speed, cashless transactions, and transparency. It's especially impactful in enhancing economic growth which is the Key momentum by accelerating digital payment systems like Immediate Payment Service, Real Time Gross Settlement, Electronic Fund Transfer, National Automated Clearing House, and Unified Payments Interface.

While the EU and China have seen significant benefits, there is limited research on their impact on India's financial system and economy.

OBJECTIVES:

- Summarize the main trends in the digital transformation of the financial sector.
- Analyze the experiences and satisfaction of customers in financial services .
- To assess the challenges associated with Fintech in financial services.
- Analyse the possibility for the transformation of the financial sector in the context of digitalization.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design:

Data Collection

The research is based on primary data and secondary data.

The primary data is acquired by a survey approach, utilizing a questionnaire, and is presented in the form of graphs.

Sources of Primary data:

- A structured questionnaire was created with 20 questions and received 100 responses.
- Respondents included 46 students, 31 lecturers or teachers, and 26 employees.

Sources of Secondary Data:

The research relied on a comprehensive literature review analysis to acquire secondary data. This comprehensive analysis included scholarly publications, industry reports, and important books about digitalization in the financial services sector. The literature research sought to discover and synthesize existing information and insights into the opportunities and challenges of digital transformation in financial services.

Sampling Techniques

Population- Research is carried out in Hubballi, Karnataka State.

Sampling Method:

Non-probability and Convenience Sampling method is used in research to collect Primary Data through structured Questionnaire. Sample size is 100 and all respondent residing in Hubballi, Karnataka State.

LIMITATIONS

- Conducting comprehensive research on digitalization in financial services requires significant resources, including funding, time, and expertise. Resource constraints can limit the depth and scope of the research.
- Data from several sources might range in quality, incomplete, obsolete, or inaccurate data might result in incorrect conclusions.
- The rapid pace at which technology is developing implies that study findings might be rendered obsolete very fast.
- Financial services digitalization includes a wide spectrum of technology such as artificial intelligence, blockchain, cloud computing, and cybersecurity. Researching this issue necessitates a thorough grasp of numerous fields, which might be difficult for researchers who specialize in one area.

DATA ANALYSIS and INTERPRETATION:

1. OCCUPATION

TABLE 1: Table showing responses from various occupations.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Students	43	43%
Lecturer or Teacher	31	31%
Employees	26	26%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 1: Table showing responses from various occupations.

INTERPRETATION:

It is observed that out of 100 respondents, majority proportionate belongs to students which are around 43% as they are the frequent users of digital payment services. Next proportionate has teaching profession which is around 31% and this group are user for mobile apps for banking services. The remaining 26% segment which consists of another professionals are users of ecommerce and net banking. All the respondents are the users of one or the other form of digitilization.

2. Which digital banking services are used most frequently?

TABLE 2: A table highlighting the most preferred digital banking services.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Mobile Banking App	63	63%
Online Application	06	06%
Digital wallets and Payments	17	17%
Investment Platforms	14	14%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 2: A graph highlighting the most preferred digital banking services.

Which digital banking services are used most frequently?
100 responses

INTERPRETATION:

Most preferable mode of usage is by using Mobile Banking App @63%, next by using digital wallets for payments. It is observed that though the numbers of students are more, yet investment platforms are not used frequently for this purpose. Applying for loan online is the least preferable as submission of application for loan has to be offline now also.

3. How long have you been investing in the financial services industry?

TABLE 3: Table displaying the duration of their investment activity in the financial services industry.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Less than 1 year	41	41%
1-3 years	26	26%
3-5 years	24	24%
More than 5 years	09	09%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 3: Graph displaying the duration of their investment activity in the financial services industry.

How long have you been investing in the financial services industry?
100 responses

INTERPRETATION:

From the table and graph, one can interpret that majority of them prefer for investment avenue for less than a year and not for long term investment of more than 5 years which is mere 9%. We can further see that investment pattern grows in ascending order alongwith the ascending order of number of years.

4. How would you rate the time efficiency of digital financial services compared to traditional methods?

TABLE 4: The table compares the time efficiency of digital financial services to traditional techniques.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Much faster	31	31%
Faster	59	59%
About the same	08	08%
Slower	01	01%
Much slower	01	01%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 4: The graph compares the time efficiency of digital financial services to traditional techniques.

How would you rate the time efficiency of digital financial services compared to traditional methods?
100 responses

INTERPRETATION:

As per the graph, it illustrates that majority of respondent agrees that digital service is much faster and faster @ 31% and 59% respectively. Only 8% respondents don't find digital financial services to be faster than the conventional method of banking. They specify that the time taken by bank staff is also same once they step in the bank.

5. What are the primary benefits you have experienced from using digital financial services?

TABLE 5: Table showing the primary benefits respondents experienced from using digital financial services.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Time savings	42	42%
Cost savings	22	22%
Improved customer service	17	17%
Access to more services	06	06%
Convenience	13	13%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 5: Graph showing the primary benefits respondents experienced from using digital financial services.

What are the primary benefits you have experienced from using digital financial services?
100 responses

INTERPRETATION:

As per the table and Graph, the prime benefits of using digital financial services is time savings @42%, other benefits proceedings are cost savings @22%, Improves customer service @17%, convenience @13% and least is for accessibility to more number of services @6%.

6. What are the main challenges faced while using digital financial services?

TABLE 6: Table outlining the primary difficulties respondents have encountered when utilizing digital financial services.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Network issues	51	51%
Security concerns	22	22%
Lack of personal interaction	15	15%
Difficulty in use	03	03%
Hidden fees or costs	08	08%
All the above	01	01%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 6: Graph outlining the primary difficulties respondents have encountered when utilizing digital financial services.

A Study on Impact of Fintech in Financial Services of Banking Sector

What are the main challenges faced while using digital financial services?
100 responses

INTERPRETATION:

As per the graph, most challenging difficult is the network issue @51% and second highest challenge is the security concerns. These challenges emerge with the higher embracing towards digitalisation. One more concern is for lack of personal interaction accounts to 15% of total difficulties respondents encounters when utilizing digital financial service.

7. Which segment of financial services has seen the most significant impact from digitalization?

TABLE 7: Table indicating the financial services industry segment that has been most affected by digitalization.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Retail banking	43	43%
Investment banking	41	41%
Insurance	11	11%
Asset management	05	05%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 7: Graph indicating the financial services industry segment that has been most affected by digitalization.

Which segment of financial services has seen the most significant impact from digitalization?
100 responses

INTERPRETATION:

As per the Graph and Table, it proves that digitalisation has being able to make significant impact across all sectors and it is most influential in retail and investment banking @41% & 43% respectively. Least preference is for Asset Management @5%. This facility is also used for paying premium of insurance @11%.

8. How has digitalization affected traditional financial service providers?

TABLE 8: Table illustrating the impact of digitization on established financial service firms.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Forced adaptation to new technologies	28	28%
Increased competition from fintech startups	25	25%
Necessitated investment in digital infrastructure	06	06%
All the above	41	41%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 8: Graph illustrating the impact of digitization on established financial service firms.

How has digitalization affected traditional financial service providers?
100 responses

INTERPRETATION:

From the above graph, it is illustrated that banking sector has to adopt to the emerging trend to facilitate their services at the global level. Due to such changes, the most impactful is forced adaptation to new technology which is @28%, it is initiative due to increased competition from fintech start-ups. Next impact is that it has necessitated investment in creating infrastructure to provide such service. Certainly all are requisite to commensurate with digitalization.

9. What is a significant risk associated with the digitalization of financial services?

TABLE 9: Table outlining the substantial risk connected with financial services digitization.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Cyber security threats	42	42%
Job deployment	24	24%
Technology dependence	21	21%
Data Privacy Concerns	13	13%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 9: Graph outlining the substantial risk connected to financial services digitization.

What is a significant risk associated with the digitalization of financial services?
100 responses

INTERPRETATION:

The above table and graph depicts the threats due to preaching of digitalization of financial services. Even with protective layers for digital financial services, they are quite prone to cyber security threats which accounts to a huge 42%. As digitalization requires less manpower to operate layoffs or job deployment are predictable and are profitable from companys point of view, which is impacted by 24%. This makes us more dependent on technology and quite eliminates traditional methods of the services, this technological dependence is observed to be @21%. As the digital services requires data to be fed into them there is a risk of the data being lost, hacked or misused which impacts at 13%.

10. Do you believe that digital financial services provide better value for money compared to traditional services?

TABLE 10: Table demonstrating that, in comparison to traditional services, digital financial services offer superior value for money.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Strongly agree	16	16%
Agree	57	57%
Neutral	26	26%
Disagree	01	01%
Strongly disagree	16	16%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 10: Graph demonstrating that, in comparison to traditional services, digital financial services offer superior value for money.

Do you believe that digital financial services provide better value for money compared to traditional services?
100 responses

INTERPRETATION:

Its astonishing that the impact accounted by “Strongly agree” and “Strongly disagree” were at 16% each. However the digitalization of the financial services have no doubt made the financial services more easier which is reflected by the impact at 57% but at some cost which could have impacted on the neutral grounds at 26% and the impact to disagree seems negligible at 1% as the digitalization makes the services convenient to use.

11. Have you ever experienced a security issue with digital financial services?

TABLE 11: Table indicating if users of digital financial services had security issues.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Yes	46	46%
No	28	28%
Maybe	26	26%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 11: Graph indicating if users of digital financial services had security issues.

Have you ever experienced a security issue with digital financial services?
100 responses

INTERPRETATION:

The above graph depicts that majority of the respondents have faced the security issues which accounts around 46% and only 1/4th of them have i.e. around 28% have not faced any issues with regards to digitalization.

12. What improvements would you like to see in digital financial services?

TABLE 12: The table displays the enhancements respondents hope to see in digital financial services.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Enhanced security	40	40%
Better user interface	23	23%
More features	22	22%
Improved customer support	14	14%
Targeted education Initiatives	01	01%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 12: The graph displays the enhancements respondents hope to see in digital financial services.

What improvements would you like to see in digital financial services?

100 responses

INTERPRETATION:

As per the table and graph, the expectations for improvements in digital financial services are obviously to enhance the security to prevent the frauds and hijacks. Next expectations is to make it a user friendly by making more convenient apps to operate.

13. Which emerging technologies do you believe will have the most impact on financial services?

TABLE 13: The table indicates that emerging technologies will have the most significant impact on financial services.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Blockchain	13	13%
Artificial Intelligence (AI)	60	60%
Machine Learning (ML)	9	9%
Fintech	18	18%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 13: The graph indicates that emerging technologies will have the most significant impact on financial services.

Which emerging technologies do you believe will have the most impact on financial services?
100 responses

INTERPRETATION:

From the graph and table, we can analyse that 60% of respondent have opted ensuring that AI is the future prospects in the banking sector and technology will play very important part in providing their services at the tip of the finger.

14. Which digital payment method do you find the most user-friendly?

TABLE 14: Table indicates the most user-friendly digital payment.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Mobile payment apps	66	66%
Digital wallets	15	15%
Online banking	12	12%
RTGS	04	04%
NEFT	03	03%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 14: Graph indicating the most user-friendly digital payment.

Which digital payment method do you find the most user-friendly?
100 responses

INTERPRETATION:

From the graph and table, it is observed that 81% of respondents use Mobile payment apps and digital wallets for their daily transactions of payment or transfers. Online banking, RTGS and NEFT are the least preferred to do the transactions. Mobile apps are frequently used rather than using laptop.

15. Which digital financial service has had the most significant impact on reaching underserved populations?

TABLE 15: A Table demonstrating the greatest influence on reaching underprivileged communities has been made by digital financial services.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Lending	27	27%
Digital Wallets	27	27%
Mobile Money Services	26	26%
Online Banking Platforms	20	20%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 15: A Table demonstrating the greatest influence on reaching underprivileged communities has been made by digital financial services.

Which digital financial service has had the most significant impact on reaching underserved populations?
100 responses

INTERPRETATION:

As per the table and graph, one can depict that the option of using digital services are many and are equally contributed by the mode of digital forms and offline mode. Peer –to-peer lending and digital wallets accounts for same proportionate around 27%. Money money services and online banking platforms are equally expanding across the boundaries.

16. How did the implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) improve financial decision-making?

TABLE 16: Table illustrating the ways in which financial decision-making was enhanced by the application of artificial intelligence.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Strongly disagree	10	10%
Disagree	11	11%
Neutral	45	45%
Agree	30	30%
Strongly Agree	04	04%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 16: Graph illustrating the ways in which financial decision-making was enhanced by the application of artificial intelligence.

how did the implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) improve financial decision-making?
100 responses

INTERPRETATION:

From the graph and the Table, we can interpret that Artificial Intelligence will be implemented and around 34% strongly agrees and agrees that Artificial Intelligence will be supportive aid to improve the financial services sector. 45% respondent remain neutral and 31% of respondents do not agree towards the influence by the role of artificial intelligence.

17. How do you think blockchain technology can improve financial inclusion globally?

TABLE 17: As seen by the table, global financial inclusion enhanced by blockchain technology.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
By enabling access to financial services for unbanked populations	28	28%
Facilitating cross-border transactions	31	31%
Providing a secure and transparent Platform for transaction	28	28%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 17: As seen in the graph, global financial inclusion enhanced by blockchain technology.

How do you think blockchain technology can improve financial inclusion globally?
100 responses

INTERPRETATION:

From the graph and the Table, we can interpret that the majority of respondents (31%) believe that facilitating cross-border transactions is the most significant way blockchain technology can improve financial inclusion globally. This is followed by enabling access to financial services for unbanked populations and providing a secure and transparent platform, each with 28% of the respondents. The least number of respondents (13%) see blockchain's role as a transaction platform as the key improvement for financial inclusion.

18. To what extent do you expect digitalization to evolve in the next decade?

TABLE 18: Table illustrating the degree to which respondents anticipate changes in digitization during the next ten years.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Significantly transform industries and daily life	37	37%
Incrementally improve existing technologies and services	28	28%
Maintain current trends without major disruptions	22	22%
Decline in relevance and impact	02	02%
Not sure	11	11%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 18: Graph illustrating the degree to which respondents anticipate changes in digitization during the next ten years.

To what extent do you expect digitalization to evolve in the next decade?
100 responses

INTERPRETATION:

From the graph and the Table, we can interpret that a significant portion of respondents (37%) anticipate that digitalization will lead to major transformations in industries and daily life, indicating high expectations for future technological advancements and their impact. A smaller, yet substantial, group (28%) expects more gradual improvements in current technologies and services, suggesting an incremental rather than revolutionary approach. 22% believe that the current pace and nature of digitalization will continue without major changes, indicating a belief in the stability and maturity of existing trends. Only a minimal percentage (2%) foresees a decline, reflecting general optimism or confidence in the ongoing relevance of digitalization. The 11% who are unsure highlight a degree of uncertainty or lack of consensus about the future trajectory of digitalization.

19. How has digitalization impacted the efficiency of financial transactions in recent years?

TABLE 19: Table illustrates the effects of digitization in recent years on the effectiveness of financial transactions.

Particular	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Increased Efficiency	55.2	55.2%
Neutral Impact	33.3	33.3%
Negative Impact	04	04%
Mixed Impact	7.3	7.3%
Total	100	100%

GRAPH 19: Graph illustrating the effects of digitization in recent years on the effectiveness of financial transactions.

How has digitalization impacted the efficiency of financial transactions in recent years?

96 responses

INTERPRETATION:

From the graph and the Table, we can interpret that a majority (55.2%) of respondents have observed increased efficiency in financial transactions, which underscores the positive role of digitalization in enhancing operational effectiveness and streamlining processes.

The significant proportion of respondents (33.3%) reporting a neutral impact indicates that while improvements are noted, they are not universal or may not be pronounced enough to be considered transformational by all. The small percentage (4%) experiencing negative impacts suggest that while generally beneficial, digitalization can also introduce challenges or inefficiencies for a minority. The mixed impact reported by 7.3% reflects diverse experiences with digitalization, possibly due to varying contexts, implementation quality, or technological adaptability.

HYPOTHESIS AND IT'S TESTING

- 1) Hypothesis for adoption of fintech for the absolute transformation and it's testing using correlation.

TABLE 20 SHOWING THE CORRELATION ADOPTION OF FINTECH			
Variables	Number of Respondents	Variables	Number of Respondents
Network issues	51	Enhanced security	40
Security concerns	22	Better user interface	23
Lack of personal interaction	15	More features	22
Difficulty in use	3	Improved customer support	14
Hidden fees or costs	9	Targeted Education Initiatives	1

Correlation **0.870508882**

Level of Significance - 0.05

H0: Adoption of Fintech for transformation is not possible

H1: Adoption of Fintech for transformation is Possible.

As per the above table, we have considered five variables for each adverse and favourable variables that influences the acceptance of adoption of the fintech. We have also considered the level of significance of 5%. We analysed the correlation between these variables which is positive and we accept that the correlation is on higher side indicating that even the adverse variables are not the constraints for converting it into favourable variable for adoption of fintech. Further, as it is more than the level of significance 0.05 than we accept the Alternate hypothesis showing the adoption of Fintech for transformation is possible inspite of all odds.

- 2) Hypothesis for prudence of the impact of fintech for the absolute transformation and it's testing using TTEST

TABLE 21 OF TTEST FOR IMPACT OF DIGITALISATION		
Factors influencing Adoption of Fintech	% of Responses	Mean
Time savings	42	17.57
Cost savings	22	-2.43
Improved customer service	17	-7.43
Access to more services	6	-18.43
Convenience	13	-11.43
Value of Money	57	32.57
Forced adaptation to new technologies	28	3.57
Increased competition from fintech startups	25	0.57
Necessitated investment in digital infrastructure	6	-18.43
Decrease in Peer-to-Peer Lending	27	2.57
Enhanced security	40	15.57
Better user interface	23	-1.43
More features enhancing efficiency of operations	22	-2.43
Improved customer support	14	-10.43
TOTAL	342	
AVERAGE	24.43	
TTEST VALUE	5.46651	

***Level of Significance – 0.05**

***Critical Value @95% confidence level is 1.96**

H0: Impact of Adoption of Fintech is negative

H1: Impact of Adoption of Fintech is positive.

As per the above table, we have considered 14 factors that influences for adoption of fintech. Factors for both before adoption and after adoption have being considered for testing the hypothesis using the TTest for the means of the samples. The result derived is above the critical value at the 95 % of confidence level and hence we reject the Null Hypothesis and accept the Alternate hypothesis indicating that the factors are absolutely in favour of blooming digitalization.

- 3) Hypothesis for prudence of the impact of fintech for the absolute transformation and it's testing using TTEST

TABLE 23 FOR CALUTION OF REGRESSION BETWEEN THE FAVOURABLE FACTORS AND ADVERSE FACTORS FOR DIGITALIZATION

Favourable Variables	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents	Particular	Adverse Variables	Percentage of Respondents
Time savings	42	42%	Network issues	51	51%
Cost savings	22	22%	Cyber security threats	46	46%
Improved customer service	17	17%	Decline in relevance	15	15%
Access to more services	6	6%	Hidden fees or costs	8	8%
Convenience	13	13%	Technology dependence	21	21%
Value of Money	57	57%	Data Privacy Concerns	13	13%

Table 24 -SUMMARY OUTPUT of Regression

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.03365
R Square	0.001132
Adjusted R Square	-0.33182
Standard Error	22.95073
Observations	5

ANOVA

	<i>Df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	1.791312	1.791312	0.003401	0.957164
Residual	3	1580.209	526.7362		
Total	4	1582			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	23.92253	18.85736	1.268604	0.294077	-36.09	83.93506	-36.09	83.93506
51	-0.04478	0.767931	-0.05832	0.957164	-2.48868	2.399117	-2.48868	2.399117

H0: The trend is assessed is not against the blooming of digitalization era in banking sector

H1: The trend is assessed is against the blooming of digitalization era in banking sector

As per the table of regression value R^2 (R Squared) is between the range of 0 and 1 than it is acceptable but when we see at the P-value, it is very high as compared to the level of significance. The P-value is 0.29 which is much higher than 0.05. This is at the edge and not beyond the critical value of confidence level indicating its acceptance too. Keeping this angle, we can observe that we accept the Null hypothesis emphasizing that the trend is not against the blooming of digitalization era and limiting constraints can be overcome.

Research Implications:

1. The data in these tables and graph (from 1 to 4) indicate that the majority of responders are young, digitally literate individuals, primarily students and professionals. They prefer mobile banking apps to other digital services as they have less investment experience, and believe digital financial services are more efficient than traditional ones. This demonstrates a trend of rising usage and good opinion of digital financial services across a young and diverse demographic.
2. The data in these tables and graph (5 and 6) state the main motivation for adopting Digital Fintech Services are convenience (42%) and cost savings (22%) because the perception of Digital Fintech Services utility and monetary gains align basically with digital infrastructure that postulates the efficiency of digital services. Security concerns are also a major issue, cited by 22% of respondents, while some also miss the personal interaction that the traditional banking offered.
3. The analysis of table and graph (7 and 9) reveals that the financial sector has bloomed with digitalisation; in fact, it has surged the retail banking as well as investment banking. In the retail banking there has been a shift to digital such as the use of online and mobile banking and use of trading system and robo advisors. Trading in securities is also influenced by automated trading platforms and big data analytics regarding investment banking. Changes in Insurance and Asset Management seem to be relatively smaller, and it may be attributed to the slow enhancement of digitalization. The biggest risks of digitalization are cyber security risks, risks of deployment, reliance on technology and risks to personal data privacy. Henceforth it may hamper the growth rate of fintech.
4. The analysis of table and graph (8 and 10) reveals that traditional financial services have without doubt been impacted with advancement in technology as they are forced to reinvest in technology to better provide their services while competing with fintech companies. The large number of customers who are indifferent or dissatisfied with the digital financial services confirms their understanding of the advantages of electronic systems and confirms a positive approach for a need on innovation and competence in the new digital age.
5. The results obtained from the consideration of tables (11 and 12) indicate the problems enumerated above are solved and that the relevance of such social online platforms is sustained. Financial institutions have to enhance the means to protect the users' data and also strive to regain the confidence of the users. This is for instance; to satisfy the need of a customer and in an attempt to make the system interactive and more effective by strengthening the user interface and features of the apps.

CONCLUSION

The trend indicates that the majorities of respondents are young students and are digitally proficient in using the digital wallets and the mobile app of bank for doing the transactions. They prefer mobile banking apps to other digital services and yet need to venture with the investment avenues. But it demonstrates a rising usage in the digital transformation in the financial sector. The study states the main motivation that people have for adopting digital fintech services are convenience (42%) and cost saving (22%) because of better utility, monetary gains and enhanced accessibility.

One of the perceived challenges is concern for network issues (22%) and security concerns which basically postulates that the efficiency verily depends upon the digital infrastructure that dwells for complete transformation using fintech services. The TTest proves that the impact of usage of fintech services is tremendous and it proves positive impact towards the spontaneous integration of technology. The regression analysis between the adverse variables and favourable variables indicates that regression exists which is minimal and can be easily overcome which is delved by the p-value figures. All correlated variables and factors need to be intricately brought in changes in the pattern of adoption in daily life.

REFERENCES

- [1] V. Acharya et al.2012, The seeds of a crisis: a theory of bank liquidity and risk-taking over the business cycle, J. Financ. Econ.
- [2] V. Acharya et al., 2019, On reaching for yield and the coexistence of bubbles and negative bubbles, J. Financ. Intermed.
- [3] A.N. Berger et al.2016, Reexamining the empirical relation between loan risk and collateral: the roles of collateral liquidity and types, J. Financ. Intermed.
- [4] D. Besanko et al.Competitive equilibrium in the credit market under asymmetric information, J. Econ. Theory
- [5] S. Bhattacharya et al., Contemporary banking theory, J. Financ. Intermed.
- [6] J. Bryant, A model of reserves, bank runs and deposit insurance, J. Bank. Financ.
- [7] G. Buchak et al. Fintech, regulatory arbitrage and the rise of shadow banks, J. Financ. Econ.
- [8] M. Carlson et al., 2018, Near-money premium, monetary policy and the integration of money markets: lessons from deregulation, J. Financ. Intermed.
- [9] H. Degryse et al., 2007, The impact of competition on bank orientation J. Financ. Intermed.
- [10] J. Donaldson et al., 2018, Warehouse banking J. Financ. Econ.
- [11] G. Cerqueiro et al.2019, Collateral damage? Priority structure, credit supply and firm performance, J. Financ. Intermed.

Citation: Dr. Veda D. Malagatti, Afsana Gudagi, Kanchan Singh, A Study on Impact of Fintech in Financial Services of Banking Sector, International Journal of Management (IJM), 15(4), 2024, pp. 177-199.

Article Link:

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJM/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_4/IJM_15_04_015.pdf

Abstract Link:

https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/IJM_15_04_015

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This work is licensed under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)**.

✉ editor@iaeme.com